

THE IMPACT OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM ON INDEPENDENT STUDY IN MIDDLE SCHOOL FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** This paper observes the impacts of flipped classroom on independent study in middle school foreign language learners. It highlights the structure of flipped lesson, its advantages, aims, and goals. After revealing this method, it started to be used globally. Observing these benefits, it is hoped that this method will be used in Uzbekistan and bring great results to language learners.*

***Keywords.** Flipped Classroom, Independent Study, Foreign Language, Middle School Learner*

Introduction. It is vividly seen that one lesson in classroom not enough for covering all stages of the lesson, that is why methodologists invented new method of teaching, flipped classroom method (FCM). According to Thieu Thi Hoang Oanh traditional classrooms have passive way of learning, lack preparation for and engagement in their lessons and lack autonomous learning skills. This situation does not create the student-centered learning environment which is being encouraged now. This situation makes it difficult to achieve the millennium education goal that is to train a global citizen with lifelong self-study skills, critical thinking, working skills in teamwork [1].

Meanwhile, in many countries in the world, the FC model has been proved to enhance students' engagement, motivation, and improves academic performance [2]. Although this method is admitted as one of the most effective ones, in the system of education of Uzbekistan it is not implemented yet. This research is devoted to show the impact of flipped classroom on independent study in middle school foreign language learners.

Languages, culture, and translation in modern linguistics: comparative approaches

According to Aslihan Unal in a flipped classroom model, students engage with lectures and other materials outside of class in order to prepare for an active learning experience in the classroom. Before classroom time, students are asked to watch short online lecture videos prepared or selected by their teachers followed by small online activities (a short quiz, online discussion, one-paragraph summary, concept map, etc.). During classroom time, students are asked to engage in concepts by participating in individual and/or group activities with the guidance of their teachers [3]. Thieu Thi Hoang Oanh states that in a FC, students watch instructional videos at home before going to the classroom and do assignments or engage in activities during the class time. With this model, classroom time can be applied to more interactive tasks. This model has been used in Europe and America recently. The main goal of flipping the classroom is to increase the face-to-face time between teachers and students and devote class time for discussing topics, answering questions and practicing exercises [1].

In Aslihan Unal's article written "Fulton listed the following among the advantages of the flipped classroom: (1) students move at their own pace; (2) doing homework in class gives teachers better insight into student difficulties and learning styles; (3) teachers can easily customize update their curriculums and provide it to students immediately; (4) classroom time can be used more effectively and creatively; (5) teachers using this method report seeing increased levels of student achievement, interest, and engagement; (6) learning theory supports the new approaches; and (7) the use of technology is flexible and appropriate for 21st Century learning" [3].

According to E.A.Kirilova the structure of the flipped classroom in learning foreign languages will be the following: firstly students will watch a video in their homes and after coming to the class make independent works on following challenges: vocabulary and collocations - independent study and analysis of lexical units by students, related to topic of the lesson); grammar - independent study grammar phenomena, fulfilling reproductive grammar exercises;

reading/listening/video comprehension - independent study with usage of several reading strategies, fulfilling exercises for understanding of read, listened and seen.

For realization flipped lesson teachers may implement wide range of technologies (Moodle, Google for education, Edmodo), video, tests, online-libraries, etc [4].

Jonathan Bergman and Aaron Sams in their book “Flip your classroom” highlighted next impacts of flipped classrooms on school students, as well as middle school learners: student–teacher interaction, student–student interaction, real differentiation, classroom management [5].

Conclusion. The flipped classroom learning encourages independent study and critical thinking which lets students to learn on their own pace. In this method classroom time is left for interactive activities, collaboration, enhancing achievements and comprehension. Flipped classroom is particularly relevant to school learners to improve their linguistic skills via independent exercises. Although this method is not integrated in Uzbekistan, however, widely used around the globe and leads to great academic results.

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